

Delinquency Proneness among Adolescents in Relation to Demographic Variables

Abstract

Adolescence is a transition period from childhood to maturity. Today we are living in 21st century and there is so much advancement in each and every sphere of our life. But with so much advancement in all fields our adolescents are deviating from their path. They are involving in anti social activities. The present study examined delinquency proneness among adolescents in relation to demographic variables of Amritsar district. Data was collected by using scale of delinquency proneness made by investigator. No significant difference was found in delinquency proneness of boys and girls and students from government and private schools, but significant difference was found among students from urban and rural area schools.

Keywords: Adolescents, Delinquency, Proneness.

Introduction

Adolescence generally refers to a period in which a person is no longer a child nor yet an adult. This is a period of rapid growth and a time of extensive re-organization and most important of human life. This period begins with puberty and ends with accession of growth. It emerges from childhood and merges into adulthood. It can be said as a transmission from childhood period to maturity in various areas i.e. physical, social, intellectual and emotional. This stage is considered as a crucial one's many aspects. A minute disposition in any way can turn them on different roads.

Rapid industrialization with its attendant urbanization, explosion in education, split in the joint family system, usage of mobiles and exposures by media has disabled a fraction of the youth all over the world from making a healthy and stable adjustment in the changing society. Change in socialization process with the adoption of western culture has made our youth more vulnerable to delinquency.

Delinquency

An adolescent is said to be delinquent when he/she is involved in such kinds of act which are not acceptable as norms of the society like stealing, assaulting and involvement in sex offences etc. The word delinquency has been derived from 'delinquere' which is comprised of two words 'de' means away and 'linquere' means 'to leave' or 'to abandon'. Generally we can say delinquency is 'falling away' from normal behavior or behavior which is not acceptable by society. Legally it means certain anti social behavioural offences which are committed by adolescents if committed by an adult would be considered as crime and shall be punishable by the court of law. Kvaraceous and Miller have reported that "Behaviour by teenagers which violates norms of a particular social institution with sufficient frequency and /or seriousness so as to provide a firm basis for legal action against the behavior of individual or group is known as delinquent behavior.

Cole "The delinquent is an individual in whom instinctive drives are strong, conscience is weak and the ego is bent upon immediate pleasure without respect to the generally accepted norms of behavior."

Isangedighi "Delinquency is a behavior that involves retraction from rules that govern behavior among adolescents. Delinquency on the whole is not an easy concept to define due to its complex characteristics. These delinquent behaviours consist of acts that violate the laws of the society."

Travis Hirschi, "The delinquency is defined by acts, the detection of which is thought to result in punishment of the person committing them by agents of the larger society."

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Education Dictionary "A delinquent is one who behaves against social norms, breaks laws, creates indiscipline in school or other institutions and disobey the rules. His immoral behavior is considered not so serious that he should be considered a culprit Juvenile courts look into his illegal behavior."

Delinquency proneness is the likelihood of an adolescent to perform anti-social act. Delinquency proneness is the probability of becoming delinquent when an adolescent is exposed to fairly common place temptations and opportunities. Thus it is the deviation from the accepted standards of the culture of a society or the laws of the land. Delinquency is not any kind of abnormality, but an acquired character.

Acchorn (1955) indicates that environment function as the precipitating force for the cause of delinquency. Mohan and Nalwa (1992) found no sex differences on the Jessness indices of delinquency proneness. Uche (1994) found that children of parents with adequate income, good occupation and high status are provided with quality private education and such children are less likely to be delinquent than their counterpart from lower socio economic background. Devi and Mayuri (2001) studied the personality profile of adolescent delinquents and concluded that boys and girls differ significantly on dimensions of guilt proneness, sensitivity and maturity. Gulati and Dutta (2004) studied the mental health profile of 245 rural adolescents (12 to 16 years) drawn from persistent poor but intact families and found delinquency as dominant problem in males while anxiety and depression in females.

Statement of the problem

Delinquency proneness among adolescents in relation to demographic variables.

Aim of the study

The aim of the study was to explore relationship of delinquency proneness with demographic variables like boys and girls, private and public schools and rural and urban schools.

Objectives of the Study

The present study was undertaken with the following objectives.

1. To investigate the significance of difference in delinquency proneness of adolescent boys and girls.
2. To investigate the significance of difference in delinquency proneness of adolescent from government and private schools.
3. To investigate the significance of difference in delinquency proneness of adolescent from rural and urban area schools.

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in delinquency proneness of adolescent boys and girls.
2. There is no significant difference in delinquency proneness of adolescents from government and private schools.
3. There is no significant difference in delinquency proneness of adolescents from rural and urban area schools.

Method

In the present study descriptive method was employed by the investigator to study the delinquency

proneness among adolescents in relation to demographic variables.

Sample

The simple random sampling technique was used and sample of 160 adolescents studying in 10+1 class of Government and private schools from rural as well as urban areas of Amritsar district were selected.

Measures

Delinquency Proneness Scale was developed by the investigator.

Statistical Techniques

t- test was used.

Table 1: Difference between Delinquency Proneness of adolescents Boys and Girls

Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	t-ratio
Boys	56	91.23	25.73	0.862 not significant
Girls	104	95.41	30.96	

Table 1 revealed that the Mean value of boys is 91.23 and Mean value of girls is 95.41 and standard deviation value of boys is 25.73 and girls is 30.96. The calculated t-value 0.862 is not significant at .05 level of confidence. It indicates that no significant difference exists in delinquency proneness among adolescent boys and girls. Hence the hypothesis that there is no significant difference in delinquency proneness of adolescent boys and girls is accepted.

Table 2: Difference between the Delinquency Proneness of adolescents from government and private schools

As seen from Table 2 the Mean value of students studying in Government schools is 93.15 and Mean value of students studying in Private schools is 94.22 and standard deviation value of students studying in Government schools is 26.96 and students studying in Private schools is 30.91. The

School	N	Mean	S.D.	t-ratio
Government	79	93.15	26.96	0.233 Not significant
Private		94.22	30.91	
	81			

calculated t-value 0.233 is not significant at .05 level of confidence which clearly indicates that there is no significant difference exists in delinquency proneness in students studying in government schools as well as in Private schools. Hence the hypothesis that there is no significant difference in delinquency proneness of adolescents from government and private schools is accepted.

Table 3: Difference between the Delinquency Proneness of adolescents from schools located in rural and urban areas

Area	N	Mean	S.D.	t-ratio
Rural	100	98.06	32.46	2.358 significant
Urban		86.95	21.47	

According to Table 3 the Mean value of students studying in Rural area schools is 98.06 and Mean value of students studying in Urban area schools is 86.95 and standard deviation value of students studying in Rural area schools is 32.46 and students studying in Urban area schools is 21.47.

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The calculated t-value 2.358 is significant at .05 level of confidence. It indicates that there is difference in delinquency proneness among students studying in rural area schools and urban area schools. Hence the hypothesis that there is no significant difference in delinquency proneness of adolescents from rural and urban schools is rejected and comparison of mean scores reveal that adolescents from rural schools are more prone to delinquency as compared to adolescents from urban schools.

Conclusion

Results revealed significant difference in delinquency proneness among adolescents from rural and urban schools. Rural adolescents are more prone to delinquency. Mistakes of adolescents at early stages should be corrected rather than ignored. Behavior of adolescents should be checked at early stages of life.

Educational Implications

The present study may help stakeholders of educational institutions in creating positive environment in the institutions so that delinquency can be checked at early stages of life.

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